

Evidence-Based Practice and its Associated Factors among Point-of-care Nurses working at the Teaching and Specialized Hospitals of Northwest Ethiopia: A Concurrent Study

Abebe Birhanu Degu*¹, Tesfahun Melese Yilma¹, Miftah Abdella Beshir¹, Anushia Inthiran²

***correspondence:**

¹ Department of Health Informatics, College of Medicine and Health Sciences, University of Gondar, Gondar, Ethiopia

² [Department of Accounting and Information Systems](#), College of Business and Law, University of Canterbury, Meremere, New Zealand

Full list of author information is available at the end of the article

Abstract

Background: Evidence-based practice (EBP) is the application of the best scientific evidence for clinical decision making in professional patient care. Most of the time, nursing care practice in Ethiopia is based on experience, tradition, intuition, common sense, and untested theories. Clinical practicing based on evidence could improve the quality of healthcare services, making it cost-effective, and improving clinical outcomes.

Methods: An institutional-based concurrent study design method of quantitative and qualitative was conducted from Feb 30 to Apr 20, 2020. Systematic random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were used to select the study participants for the quantitative and qualitative, respectively. Quantitative data were collected using a pretested, structured, and self-administered questionnaire, and the qualitative data were collected by an in-depth interview guiding questions.

Results: EBP was found to be significantly associated with educational level (AOR=2.15, CI (1.15-4.02)), administrative support for EBP (AOR=1.89, CI (1.22-2.91)), attitude towards EBP (AOR=1.80, CI (1.24-2.62)), and preference of available information sources (AOR: 2.32, CI: (1.58-3.39)). Four main themes arose by conventional content data analysis: (1) advantages of the application of EBP (2) barriers for the implementation of EBP (3) Enabling factors for EBP and (4) Sharing of evidence.

Conclusion: This study concluded that a small number of nurses applied EBP to a high level. There was a positive association between educational level, attitude towards EBP, administrative support, the availability of information resources with implementation of EBP and it was confirmed by the qualitative study. There has to be an intervention program to facilitate the implementation of evidence in nursing practice by the stakeholders to improve and increase the efficacy of practicing EBP.

Keywords: *Evidence-Based Practice, Nursing Practice, Ethiopia*

Background

Evidence-based practice (EBP) is the application of the best scientific evidence in clinical decision-making by integrating clinical experience and incorporating patient values and preferences, in the practice of professional patient care (1). It is about making decisions by using the best available evidence from multiple sources in a conscientious, explicit, and judicious manner (2).

Evidence is information based on historical or scientific evaluation of practices that can be accessible to decision-makers in the health care system. The types of evidence considered acceptable include: experimental (randomized clinical trials, meta-analyses, and analytic studies); non-experimental (quasi-experimental, observational); expert opinion and historical or experiential (3).

Nursing is a science that is essential to draw knowledge from research findings. Scientific research is the standard by which knowledge is derived from science. Practice in nursing is the source of research questions, while research is the basis of current practice. Therefore, practice and research exist with each other in a circular continuum (4).

Currently, EBP, which is the use of theoretical research-based findings together with reliable forms of evidence in clinical decision-making, is essential to nursing practice to promote optimal patient outcomes by incorporating research findings, the experience of clinicians, and patient preferences (5).

EBP has been recognized as the gold standard for the delivery of compassionate and safe care as well as promoting excellence in nursing care. Despite the exploding availability of healthcare information and the ongoing pressure by authorities, the application of research-based evidence in nursing practice is limited; the care of the patient was influenced by the experiences and opinions of those involved in providing treatment. Studies consistently show that interventions have failed to be effective and cost-effective in worldwide (6).

EBP is not widely embraced in low- and middle-income countries. EBP methods are a relatively new and often overwhelming challenge for many healthcare organizations. For

example, in Africa such as South Africa, Ethiopia, Kenya, Nigeria, Egypt, Botswana, Burundi, and Malawi EBP is emphasized and promoted for nurses (7-10). Yet, the development of EBP in nursing practice is in its infancy stage. For example, a recent study from Nigeria reported that EBP is not widely developed in the context of the country's health care system (7). EBP in Africa is remaining challenging. One reason for this challenge is Africa lags in research because limited studies are describing the state of the art of EBP and the lack of funding from the government (10). Another possible reason is due to limited resource which makes it almost impossible for health professionals to work with vulnerable communities to access information in low-income settings (11).

Nurses may not have the skill or expertise on how to obtain the research evidence from the literature or how to apply the evidence, which makes it cost-ineffective, none improving clinical outcomes, obstacles towards transferring research into clinical practice, and challenging the adoption process (12). Such a situation produces medical errors such as miss diagnosis, wrong treatment, increase in multidrug resistance, severe iatrogenic injuries, and unexpected patient death which are common in today's health care services (13, 14).

The nursing staff is the largest health professional group in all health care sectors who are working in the direct care of patients, assessing patients' needs, and making decisions on nursing interventions that will stay for a long period (15). However, at all levels of the health systems, there is little culture or tradition of conducting, trusting, or using EBP by nurses (16).

Even though several studies have attempted to analyze EBP from different perspectives, the detailed factors are not analyzed, especially in developing countries like Ethiopia and also in the study area while professional development and information communication technologies (ICT) are becoming more advanced. If nurses do perform EBP that would be beneficial for continuous education, continuous learning, improved knowledge, and overall be able to increase the quality of care given to patients. Additionally, it is not known how much health-related research is being utilized to improve healthcare practice to ensure high-quality healthcare delivery and improve standards and quality of life. Hence, this study aimed to assess Evidence-Based Practice and its associated factors among nurses working at the study settings.

Methods

Research Design and Setting

An institution-based concurrent study design using quantitative and qualitative methods was conducted from 30 Feb to 20 Apr 2020. This research was carried out in the two governmental teaching and specialized hospitals of the Amhara Regional State, Northwest Ethiopia (the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion), serving 3.5–5 million people each. The hospitals are the only teaching and specialized hospitals in the Amhara region. They are selected because:

- They are training centers for professional development as in-service and out-service for health professionals in addition to undergraduate and postgraduate medical students.
- They have a reputation for research excellence since they are staffed with the most senior specialists who manage patients with complex illness and are exposed to highly specialized care with well resourced diagnostic and therapeutic facilities as a larger referral center in the region.
- They have strategic goals to produce evidence-based health care professionals with a culture of continuous professional development and improved patient care.
- They are serving as a practical educational site for students and healthcare providers in addition to their daily patient care so nurses are expected to implement EBP.

Research Participants

Inclusion criteria: This study was included all nurses having a Bachelor of Science (BSc) and above in nursing who are working at the study settings.

Exclusion criteria: This study was excluded nurses who were on leave (annual, maternal, and/or sick leave), having less than six-month of work experience, nurses who were on postgraduate programs, and nurses of academic staffs since postgraduate program followers/students were not eligible during the data collection period and

Nurses involved in academic staff were believed to have better EBP experience in their academic activities (17), who skewed the results of the study.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was calculated using both the single and double population proportion formula.

Single population proportion formula:

$$n = \frac{(Z_{\alpha/2})^2 * p * (1-p)}{(d)^2}$$

Where, z = 95% confidence level, d = 5% margin of error, and 51.8% proportion (p) of EBP from previous study (16). Assuming a 10% non-response rate, the total sample size became 423.

Double population proportion formula:

We have calculated the sample size for each factor variables from the previous study (16). Power =80%, confidence level 95%, OR 1:1 (Table: 1 see [Additional file 1](#))

Then taken the highest sample size i.e. 482 and assumed the non-response rate of 10 % (482) =48 the final sample size was determined to be 482+48=530.

Sampling Procedures

The study participants were selected proportionally from the two hospitals. The lists of nurses in each hospital were used as a sampling frame for identifying possible study participants in the sample. All nurses working at the same hospital were assumed to be homogeneous for EBP. Participants of the study were then randomly selected using record identification numbers taken from the sampling frame. The lottery method was used to randomly pick nurses as study participants (Fig 1 see [Additional file 2](#)).

Among 530 candidate study participants a total of 507 BSc and above nurses, who returned the questionnaire were taken from 10 administrative nurses, 34 nurses' team leaders, whereas 463 as staff nurses by simple random sampling.

For an in-depth interview 12 key informants were taken by convenience till information saturation has been made. The key informant selection criteria were both professional and practical experience (clinical staff and/or management). The first selection criterion was to work at least during the last 6 months in the hospital. Upon meeting these criteria, nurses were divided into the following groups: 1. Administrative nurses group (G ADM) 2. Team leader nurses group (G TEAM) and 3. Clinical Staff nurses: additionally, these nurses were subdivided into three groups:

- 3.1. Less than 5 years of experience in the hospital (G STA<5),
- 3.2. Between 5 and 10 years of experience in the hospital (G STA5–10),
- 3.3. More than 10 years of experience in the hospital (G STA > 10).

Data Collection Tools and Procedures

Data were collected using a pretested and structured self-administered questionnaire which was mostly adapted from various studies conducted in Ethiopia previously (10, 16, 18) and some of them were adopted from various studies (19, 20) (see Additional file 5). The questionnaire was prepared in English as the study subjects were BSc and above nurse professionals who are believed to be proficient in English. For the in-depth interview, the guiding questions were prepared and translated into the local language (Amharic) for its simplicity, validity, and clarity.

Moreover, the questionnaire was pretested among 5% of the sample size at Felege Hiwot Referral Hospital, and questionnaire reduction, jargon words elimination, grammar correction, etc. were done. The reliability of the tool for each subscale was checked using Cronbach's alpha reliability test (0.91), which indicated sufficient reliability of parameters in the questionnaire.

Quantitative data were collected from nurses by one BSc nurses and one health informatics profession through distributing structured self-administered questioner for the nurses after explaining the purpose and technique of filling the questionnaire. The Principal Investigator (PI) has done continuous monitoring and supervision throughout the data collection period.

Qualitative data was collected by the PI from key informants. Key informants took for an in-depth interview based on purposive convenience sampling. Every in-depth interview had been taken 30-35 minutes. Notes and audio recorders have been used to record information from key informants.

The questionnaire of the quantitative study were consisted of eight sections: about EBP, Knowledge, Preferences/Use of available information sources, Awareness about Electronic Information Sources, Information searching skill, Nurses Self-Efficacy, Attitude, and Factors associated with evidence-based practice. Each section had its own number of subscale having greater than seven questions made by different researchers which measures it.

In total, seven self-reported questions were asked to test EBP. Each question had a response scale of four points (never, monthly, weekly, and daily). These categories were marked from 1 to 4 as numerical values (Never '1', Monthly '2', Weekly '3', Daily '4'). Respondent, therefore, had a total score of EBP (from a minimum of 7 to a possible maximum of 28). The average of each question can be calculated as $(1+2+3+4)/4 = 2.5$. Answering above 2.5 was considered as desirable responses to the EBP questions. EBP was assessed by using the average score of the seven questions. Hence, $2.5 \times 7 = 17.5$ is used as the cut-off point. Respondents having a total EBP score above the cut of point 17.5 were considered as having 'Good EBP' while those below were labeled as having 'Poor EBP'.

In total, 10 questions showing the extent of EBP knowledge, each of which had a Yes, No, and I don't know (IDK) answer, was asked. Yes, answers are coded as '1', and 'no', and I don't know (IDK) as '0'. A cumulative EBP knowledge score (from at least 0 up to a maximum of 10) was determined for all respondents. After checking for normal distribution the mean knowledge score was calculated to test the knowledge score using Shapiro–Wilk test (21) ($W = 0.982$ and $p = 0.11$) and a visual inspection of their histogram, normal Q-Q plots, and box plots showed that knowledge scores were approximately normally distributed with a skewness = -0.167 ($SE = 0.218$), kurtosis of -0.247 ($SE = 0.433$) and mean = 6 ($SD = \pm 1.73$). Respondents having knowledge score above the mean value considered as 'good knowledge' unless as 'poor knowledge'.

The level of attitude towards EBP was determined in ten questions. Every question of attitude had a Likert scale of five points (strongly agreed coded as 5, agreed coded as 4, neutral coded as 3, disagreed coded as 2, and strongly disagreed coded as 1). Each respondent had a cumulative attitude score of at least 10 points to a possible maximum of 50 points. The attitude towards an EBP score was tested for normal distribution using the Shapiro Wilk test ($W= 0.983$, $p= 0.589$) and a visual inspection of their histogram, normal Q-Q plots, and box plots showed that attitude scores were approximately normally distributed with a skewness= 0.015 ($SE=0.316$), kurtosis of -0.206 ($SE=0.623$) and mean= 36 ($SD=\pm 3.921$). Respondents with an attitude above the mean score towards evidence-based practice were classified as 'favorable attitude' and those below were categorized as 'unfavorable attitude'.

In total, six questions to measure the level of respondents' skill towards Information Searching skills (skill in finding, reviewing, and using different sources of evidence) had a Likert scale of five points (very good coded as 5, Good coded as 4, neither good nor poor coded as 3, poor coded as 2, and very poor coded as 1). For all respondents, a total EBP skill score (from a minimum of 6 up to a possible maximum of 30) was determined. The mean skill score was calculated after checking for normal distribution to test the skill score using the Shapiro–Wilk test (21) ($W= 0.971$, $p= 0.09$) and a visual inspection of their histogram, normal Q-Q plots, and box plots showed that skill scores were approximately normally distributed with a skewness= -0.124 ($SE= -0.279$), kurtosis of -0.206 ($SE= 0.552$) and mean= 19 ($SD=2.968$) and label respondents having skill scores above the mean value as 'good skill' unless as 'poor skill'.

In total, seven questions were provided to measure the use of available information sources with a Likert scale of five points (never "1", rarely "2", sometimes "3", often "4" and always "5"). The mean use score was calculated after checking for normal distribution to test the use score using the Shapiro–Wilk test (21) ($W= 0.945$, $p= 0.79$) and a visual inspection of their histogram, normal Q-Q plots, and box plots showed that preference scores were approximately normally distributed with a skewness= -0.249 ($SE= 0.398$), kurtosis of 0.335 ($SE= 0.495$) and mean= 12.8 ($SD=0.474$) and label

respondents having use scores above the mean value as 'preferred available information source' unless as 'not preferred'.

Eleven questions were provided to measure awareness of electronic information sources with a Likert scale of three points (unaware "1", aware but not used in clinical decision making "2", aware and used "3"). The mean awareness score was calculated after checking for normal distribution to test the awareness score using the Shapiro–Wilk test (21) ($W= 0.969$, $p= 0.197$) and a visual inspection of their histogram, normal Q-Q plots, and box plots showed that awareness scores were approximately normally distributed with a skewness= -0.004 ($SE=0.333$), kurtosis of -0.368 ($SE= 0.656$) and mean= 14 ($SD=0.487$) and label respondents having awareness scores above the mean value as 'aware electronic information source' unless as 'not aware'.

Seven questions were provided to measure the self-efficacy of nurses with a Likert scale of three points (not confident "1", moderately confident "2" and confident "3"). The mean self-efficacy score was calculated after checking for normal distribution to test the self-efficacy score using the Shapiro–Wilk test (21) ($W= 0.981$, $p= 0.258$) and a visual inspection of their histogram, normal Q-Q plots, and box plots showed that preference scores were approximately normally distributed with a skewness= 0.172 ($SE= 0.267$), kurtosis of -0.302 ($SE= 0.529$) and mean= 14.72 ($SD=0.307$) and label respondents having self-efficacy scores above the mean value as 'confident' unless as 'not confident'.

Data Management and Analysis

First, the data were coded and entered into Epi-data version 4.6.0 (Epi-Data Entry is used for simple or programmed data entry and data documentation. It handles simple forms or related systems Optimized documentation and error detection features) and exported to SPSS version 20 for analysis. Data analysis includes descriptive statistics to describe the demographic characteristics of the participants, and the data were described using text, tables, and graphs. A Chi-square test was done for all categorical independent variables. Variance inflation factor (VIF) was used to check multi-collinearity. Binary logistic regression was used to determine the association between the outcome variables and predictors. Statistical tests at 95% CI and $P\text{-value} \leq 0.05$ were

made. Variables having a p-value of up to 0.2 in the bi-variable analysis were selected to fit the model in the multivariable analysis. Finally, a P-value ≤ 0.05 in the multivariable model of logistic regression was used to select variables that had a statistically significant association with EBP. (See Additional file 3 and 4)

The qualitative data was taken by Amharic and then transcribed and interpreted in English. A thematic analysis was carried out through an inductive coding process. The researcher carried out the coding procedure to ensure the rigorous and credible of the analysis. Through this triangulation process, in a first reading of the data, the researcher identified emerging topics and patterns and drew up a list of possible topics that were then used to set up the codes based on Lundman and Graneheim data analysis approach. Data reduction was carried out by matching codes and setting relationships and analogies. The qualitative data analysis was assisted by the Open code software.

Trustworthiness was determined by using a technique of prolonged engagement with participants, persistent observation, peer-debriefing and member-checking. Evidence was also presented by iterative questioning of the data, and returning to examine it several times.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of the University of Gondar. Official letters of support were presented to the study settings and the intents and the grandness of the subject were explained and verbal informed consent was obtained from each participant. Participants were informed that all data obtained from them are maintained confidentially and anonymously by using codes instead of personal identifiers.

Results

Socio-Demographic Characteristics

A total of 530 questionnaires were distributed to the study participants with 507 of the questionnaires being returned (response rate of 95.7%). Of the returned questionnaires, 340 (67.1%) and 167 (32.9%) were from the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion teaching specialized hospitals respectively. The respondents were 273 (53.8%) female and 234 (46.2%) male, 463 (91.3%) were staff nurses, and 34 (6.7%) were team lead nurses and 10 (2.0%) administrative nurses. Of the 507 study subjects, the mean age was 29.71(SD±4.42). Most of the subjects in the study were BSc, which accounts for 447 (88.2%), only 128 (25.2%) were got training related to EBP from 68 (13.4%) undergraduate and 60 (11.8%) postgraduate. The detailed information is provided in Table 2. ([Table: 2 See Additional file 1](#))

Evidence-Based Practice in the study area

Of the total 507 nurses, 239 (47%) [95% CI of 43% to 51%] had incorporated EBP into their clinical practice. Their practice rate was assessed with three options (sometimes / monthly, usually / weekly, and always / daily) by self-reporting. Just 160(32%), 216(43%), and 76 (15%) apply EBP monthly, weekly, and always or regularly in their clinical practice respectively ([Fig: 2 See Additional file 2](#)).

Knowledge about evidence-based practice

Once asked how familiar the respondents were with the concept, about 441 (87%) were familiar with the concept of EBP with a mean knowledge of 6 (SD±12.9). When the respondents asked questions about research terms about 217 (42.8%) of respondents scored low, and about 290 (57.2%) of respondents scored high with 58% [95% CI of 56.2% to 59.2%] of overall knowledge.

Preferences/Use of available information sources for Evidence-Based Practice

We found that human information sources (sharing with colleagues), using medical applications, and policy and guidelines were used more frequently by them. It was

worthy of notice that the use of electronic information sources (medical journals and databases) among nurses was the least common ([Fig: 3 See Additional file 2](#)).

Awareness about Electronic Information Sources for Evidence-Based Practice

The majority of nurses have relatively aware and used medical applications such as Medscape than the different medical journals and databases of electronic information sources as seen in ([Fig: 4 See Additional file 2](#)).

Information searching skill for Evidence-Based Practice

Most nurses (60%) are unlikely to skim down or quickly browse resources. There are some problems, such as lack of information technology skills, access to research articles, lack of references in the native language that most research is published in a foreign language.

Even though participants had overall information searching skill of 64%, It was worth remembering that several nurses have revealed that they are not comfortable with Boolean and proximity operators (54%) ([Fig: 5 See Additional file 2](#)).

Nurses Self-Efficacy in Evidence-Based Practice

The majorities (71%) of nurses have no confidence but, only 5% of nurses have confidence in their decision-making of day-to-day clinical practice ([Fig: 6 See Additional file 2](#)).

Attitude towards evidence-based practice

Respondents had a mean attitude score of 36 (SD±3.92), however, Fifty-five percent of respondents had a favorable attitude towards EBP. Based on the findings, 71% of respondents agreed that research and literature findings are useful in day-to-day practice, 58.5% of respondents agreed that EBP improves the quality of healthcare while 23.1% agreed that their reimbursement rate would increase if they incorporated EBP into their practice ([Fig:7 See Additional file 2](#)).

Factors associated with evidence-based practice

When asked about barriers that impeded their EBP, 52% of the participant reported that there were barriers to EBP implementation. The identified barriers includes: availability of information sources 16%(n=41), computer access 89%(n=235), internet access 89.7%(n=237), internet speed 53%(n=140), administrative support 74%(n=195), search strategy and EBP training 80%(n=211), enough time for practice 56%(n=148), awareness about EBP 58%(n=153), understanding literatures in foreign language 28%(n=74), authority to change 54%(n=143), physicians cooperation 55%(n=145), understanding statistical terms 54%(n=143), literatures have conflicting report 66%(n=174) and lack of resources 76%(n=201). Some respondents identified more than one barrier.

Qualitative result analysis

For an in-depth interview 12 BSc and above (7 staffs, 3 team leaders and 2 administrative) nurse key informants were selected purposively from 113 BSc and above nurses who were not selected for quantitative until the data was saturated.

Four main themes arose by conventional content data analysis: (1) advantages of the application of EBP (2) barriers for the implementation of EBP (3) Enabling factors for EBP (4) Sharing of evidence

1. Advantages on the application of EBP

This theme addressed what participants perceived as a constructive outcome when relying on data for their research and clinical practice, and that EBP decreases the uncertainty in clinical practice.

"I think we all operate in the same way that we have the best healthcare." (G ADN) (M1)

They also believed that evidence-based healthcare provided a higher quality of care for patients and made the most of the resources and time available:

"I think you'll give more appropriate treatment to patients if you base yourself on the facts. For fewer resources, you can produce better outcomes."(G TEAM) (M1)

Participants claimed that scientifically based clinical practice improves professional image and gives legal support.

“I believe that it makes the profession more valuable and reinforces it. Then, it is a back-up when you say. Well, we’re working on a scientific method.” (G TEAM) (M2)

They said that the EBP is encouraging and that it is both a challenge and motivation.

“Yes, I think so, too, when you see people doing things, you feel like doing things, too. When you go to another place where people are settled, they don't care about anything, and they just go to meet their work schedule...” (G STA >10) (F1)

“I would love to base the evidence on all my work. I will be happy if I could investigate at work. . . .” (G STA 5–10) (F2)

EBP leads to an awareness of what it means to be a nurse and what its professional responsibility is. Also, EBP entrusts the patient with a professional commitment.

“Yet, where do our shortcomings lie? We have to know them and know when we are doing our job properly...” (G STA 5- 10) (M1)

“Then, I have to do research, I have to answer this person who is coming and telling me something about Tuberculosis. . . .” (G TEAM) (M1)

2. Barriers to the application of EBP

Obstacles to applying EBP have arisen more often than the gains from its implementation. One participant noted the lack of incentives to encourage and recognize EBP, and stressed the importance of institutional support and motivation:

“In a way, I believe that it should be the responsibility of nursing management to motivate, encourage, and generate interest in nurses, and I do not know how. I think training needs to come first and then encouragement.” (G STA 5–10) (F2)

“We clinical staff need our higher administrator's support in conducting clinical research because we know our problem more than academic staff, so if we have the opportunity to investigate our clinical problem, we can integrate research evidence into our everyday practices.” (G STA 5–10) (M2)

Nurses do not agree that variables such as finances, the type of patient, or professional characteristics are taken into account when designing protocols or clinical practice guidelines:

“To start the protocol process, do we take into account the needs of each population group in which we work? This doesn't seem so, as it takes them into account when applying. . .” (G STA >10) (M3)

“Training center has to be established to give training for us on how to integrate research evidence in our practices and to develop guidelines for practice, thus serving as a source for guiding our health interventions” (G STA<5) (F3)

Participants found that various health practitioners dispute the clinical procedure. They mentioned the burden the hospital specialists placed on them, the patients, their colleagues, and the lack of written scientific documentation:

“The patients who push and tell you another nurse healed them the previous day and they did so differently and they are the ones who force you to do so. . .” (G STA >10) (F1)

“Throughout obtaining information and knowledge-based preparation are not provided and there is a lack of understanding and provision that the practitioner can work through the facilitator throughout developing a documentary environment.” (G STA 5-10) (F4)

Participants were also very tired and frustrated with institutional help in their efforts to bring about sounder hospital improvements:

“We have just attended a conference, haven't we? Obscure things have we known, have we not? Then you send a session and say, look, it is explained here, not proof-based. The next day, you find out that they continue to do the same. It doesn't matter. . .” (G STA 5- 10) (M1)

Concerning the obstacles, doubts about new evidence and resistance to change were the most common problems mentioned. In all interviewees, weak arguments were presented as excuses for not applying EBPs, such as their complexity, and the lack of appropriate clinical resources and studies.

“Now that we are trying to apply EBP, yes, it is very complicated to be wondering all the time if you are doing it correctly.” (G STA 5–10)(M2)

“... No hospital library, revised rules, inspiration, adequate training, and computers to enable nurses to upgrade.” (G STA 5–10) (F2)

Participants also doubted the findings should be used in clinical practice:

“Instead, I believe the scientific method is very good, offering the career and all, but I do not think we need to become robots simply because it has been proved.” (G STA >10) (M3)

Participants agreed that, even though a theoretical foundation supports the new approach, it is very difficult for them to alter norms already developed. In every interview, this segment was addressed thoroughly, particularly in the interview with less experienced staff:

“It is difficult to change the first problem you face. People say to you: No, I always did so, so it works well.” (G STA 5–10)(M2)

They also mentioned an inadequate knowledge of EBP methodology:

“The first challenge is adapting, then, and preparing so that I can do it, and then, it's doubt, what if I do something wrong? What if I can't do that?” (G ADM) (M1)

3. Enabling factors for EBP

This theme included what participants regarded as an EBP facilitator.

“even if it is not enough sometimes there is training for some nurses, makes the Internet accessible to all professionals, training on information sources and methods of use, due to inadequate training and inadequacy of authority to change procedure of care, the nurses are unable to provide services based on a patient's informed choice.” (G STA 5–10) (F2)

“Training center has to be established to give training for us on how to integrate research evidence in our practices and to develop guidelines for practice, thus serving as a source for guiding our health interventions” (G STA<5) (F3)

4. Sharing of evidence

Concerning how new evidence is shared, all participants agreed that they do not receive formal working time during which they were taught by non-hospital experts, as well as by nurses from the hospital, who preferred to participate in the work:

“In the sessions, we try to share it. For example, one of our colleagues has held an injection workshop because he knows that.” (G STA5-10) (F4)

“For if you say that I know nothing about it and that someone comes and does it, it means that you don't matter what you do.” (G STA >10) (M3)

In situations and contexts not specifically designed to share scientific data, EBP has occasionally been promoted.

“It's usually in the tea break many times when we say: remember what we talked about a few days ago? Do you remember? That's a scientific paper I've found. . .” (G TEAM) (M1)

Participants further discussed variations in clinical quality and quantity and other methods of EBP sharing between hospitals.

“The difference is so vast that I have been working in several health centers and hospitals” (G STA>10) (F1)

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to assess Evidence-Based Practice and its associated factors among Nurses working at the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals, Amhara Region, Northwest Ethiopia.

This study was obtained findings as a low prevalence of EBP, and associated factors eligible for EBP were educational level, the attitude of Nurses towards EBP use, administrative support, and Preferred available information sources.

In this study, EBP among nurses of the study settings was found to be 47%. Only 207(41%), 174(34%), and 57 (11%) apply/use EBP in their clinical practice monthly, weekly, and always or daily respectively. This finding was consistent with the study done in Tikur Anbesa hospital in Addis Ababa, in which 57.6% of participants applied EBP. Of them, 64 (52.8%), 38 (31.4%), and 19 (15.7%) applied EBP sometime, usually, and always respectively (10). This was inconsistent with the finding of Nigeria (22) where 55.5% and 30.9% of nurses sometimes and often used EBP respectively. This suggests nurses working in the current study area were less likely to use EBP than in other countries. It may be due to the Nurse's tendency to use more traditional resources such as colleagues and other medical professionals than up-to-date resources such as electronic resources and journals to make clinical decisions.

This result was also confirmed by the in-depth interview, *“Since there are no guidelines available for practicing evidence-based nursing in my workplace, I am not working my job based on the facts that are supported by updated best evidence, I only job by sharing the problems with my colleague's opinions ”* (G STA>10) (F1)

“I only work with the knowledge that I have gained from my education, and sometimes I use Google to update my practice records”. (G STA 5- 10) (M1)

“... No hospital library, updated guidelines, motivation, enough training, and no enough computers for nurses for updating themselves.” (G STA 5–10) (F2)

The odds of EBP among nurses with MSc and above were 2.148 times higher (AOR= 2.15, 95%CI= (1.15-4.02)) when compared to BSc nurses (Table: 3 see Additional file 1). This is a contrast with the study of Nigeria (22) in which professional qualification has no relationship with the use of good EBP but is analogous with the finding of a

study done in Ethiopia (16). It suggests that good EBP was most often used by nurses who had higher qualifications than by lower qualifications. This may be because the educational level MSc and above are more technically oriented, improving quest techniques, or being more open to the introduction of EBP into their curricula and teaching programs.

The attitude of nurses towards the integration of evidence-based practice in their clinical practice accounted for 72%. This finding was similar to the study conducted In South Africa 75% (23) and Singapore 64% (19). In our finding, the odds of EBP among nurses having a favorable attitude was 1.80 times higher (AOR=1.80, 95%CI= (1.24-2.62)) when compared to unfavorable attitudes. This finding agrees with the studies conducted in South Africa (19). This may be due to the difference in nurses' qualification level, work experience, and training which have the potential to significantly enhance beliefs and attitudes about EBP. Nurses with a higher level of qualification have better knowledge, which improves their attitude towards EBP.

This result was also confirmed by the in-depth interview in which most of the respondents suggest *"It is important for quality care, but the workload, lack of knowledge and training make us follow previous experience or rely on opinions of experts."*

The odds of EBP among nurses having administrative support were 1.89 times higher (AOR=1.89, 95%CI= (1.22-2.91)) when compared to having no support. This is in line with the study conducted in Ethiopia (10). Other studies also identified managers, not only as a key factor for the generation and implementation of EBCP but also for the creation of a good research environment (24).

It was confirmed by the qualitative as:

Most participants believed that *"they need training and budget support for evidence"*

"Training center has to be established to give training for us on how to integrate research evidence in our practices and to develop guidelines for practice, thus serving as a source for guiding our health interventions" (G STA<5) (F3)

"We clinical staff need our higher administrator's help in conducting clinical research because we know our problem better than academic staff, and if we get the chance to

perform research on our clinical issue, we can do and incorporate research evidence into our daily practices". (G STA 5–10) (M2)

The odds of EBP among nurses Preferred available information sources were 2.32 times higher (AOR: 2.32, 95%CI: 1.58-3.39) when compared to counterpart. This study is consistent with prior studies (25, 26) which found that human information sources and sources of print information were used more frequently by them. This was presumably because of their higher usability and the ease of using them and having less Internet access, lowers device use, and less participation in online activities. It was worth noting that the use of electronic information sources by nurses was the least common, given the fact that they have low ability, interpersonal and technical competence of information searching skill of the latest research information.

It was confirmed as:

The majority of nurses said, "We need training on how to use evidence from journals and databases, and how to search for literature to provide effective interventions in health care".

"...their desire to use the information is as poor as possible because the profession does not do as much as the profession allows, the nurse professional does not have a culture of communicating and learning one another. So, we need training on how to use evidence from and how to search for literature from databases to provide effective health care interventions." (G STA >10) (M3)

Strength

- This study used both quantitative and qualitative research design to analyze some factors associated with EBP
- A pretest was conducted to test the tools and overall procedures of the study
- Unlike other studies, it has a 95.7% response rate.
- This study was conducted in two of the Amhara regional state teaching specialized hospitals (the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion), which enables the generalizability of the results to other teaching specialized hospitals of Ethiopia.

Limitations

- To compare in a local context, no more previously studied researches were available in Ethiopia.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study have implications for practice, education, policy, and research. It will be supremely significant to the policymakers and more specifically to the nursing and health care professionals to provide quality of care in meeting the needs of patients and families as a whole specifically it improves patient outcomes.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concluded that a small number of nurses applied EBP to a high level. The implementation of evidence-based practice was associated with educational level, attitude towards EBP, administrative support, and the availability of information resources and it was confirmed by the qualitative study. There has to be an intervention program to facilitate the implementation of evidence in nursing practice by the respective stakeholders (Ethiopian Federal Ministry of Health, Amhara Regional Health Bureau, educators of nursing education, and hospital administration of Amhara Region Teaching Referral public hospitals).

Training should be conducted for nurses on the implementation of evidence-based practice by Amhara Region Teaching Referral public hospitals in collaboration with NGOs, the Ethiopian Federal Ministry of Health, and the Amhara Regional Health Bureau. Resources necessary to implement evidence-based nursing practice should be provided by hospital administration in collaboration with the Ethiopian Federal Ministry of Health, Amhara Regional Health Bureau, and other NGOs. Intervention programs concerning organizational communication with issues on evidence-based practice implementation should be done together with nurses to create supportive staff by the nursing administration of the study setting. Since there is a gap of attitude towards evidence-based nursing practice curriculum planners should take into consideration to include the principle of evidence-based nursing practice in Ethiopian nursing education programs especially in the undergraduate nursing education curriculum.

Abbreviations

AOR: adjusted odds ratio, CI: Confidence interval, COR: Crude odds ratio,

EBP: Evidence-Based Practice, G ADM: Group of nurses with Administrative responsibilities, G TEAM: Group of nurses with team leader responsibilities,

G STA<5: Group of Staff nurses with less than 5 years of professional experience, G

STA5–10: Group of Staff nurses with professional experience ranging from 5 to 10

years and G STA > 10: Group of Staff nurses with more than 10 years of professional experience.

Declarations:

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by an institutional ethical review committee of the University of Gondar and written informed consent was obtained from each study participant. Permission letters were also obtained from each hospital. All the data used in this manuscript were privately available and confidentiality was maintained anonymously.

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

No funding.

Availability of data and materials

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study will be available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

Authors' contributions

AB selected the title, developed the proposal, collect the data, analyzed the data, interpreted the results, and prepared the manuscript. TM and MA assisted the design,

comment, and approve the proposal, thesis, and the manuscript. AI assisted in the preparation of the manuscript and commented and edited the manuscript. All authors have read and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the Institute of Public Health, College of Medicine and Health Science, University of Gondar. Our thanks also extended to the participating nurses for their cooperation in this study.

Authors' information

Abebe Birhanu Degu (BScN, MPH in Health Informatics); **Tesfahun Melese Yilma** (BSc, MPH, Ph.D.); **Miftah Abdella Beshir** (BSc, MPH); **Anushia Inthiran** (BSc, MSc, PhD).

Authors' Detail

¹ Department of Health Informatics, College of Medicine and Health Sciences, University of Gondar, Gondar, Ethiopia

² Department of Accounting and Information Systems, College of Business and Law, University of Canterbury, Meremere, New Zealand

References

1. Melnyk BM, Fineout-Overholt E. **Evidence-based practice in nursing & healthcare: A guide to best practice**: *Lippincott Williams & Wilkins*; 2011. 208-224.
2. Banning MJJoCN. Conceptions of evidence, evidence-based medicine, evidence-based practice, and their use in nursing: independent nurse prescribers' views. 2015;14 (4):411-417.
3. Tranmer Ja, Squires S, Brazil K, Gerlach J, Johnson J, Muisiner D, et al. **Factors that influence evidence-based decision-making**. 1998; 5:3-92.
4. Kristensen N, Nymann C, Konradsen HJBhsr. **Implementing research results in clinical practice-the experiences of healthcare professionals in Denmark**. *BMC Health Service Research*. 2015;16(1):48.
5. Mokhtar IA, Majid S, Foo S, Zhang X, Zheng Y-L, Chang Y-K, et al. **Evidence-based practice and related information literacy skills of nurses in Singapore: an exploratory case study**. *Malaysian Journal of Literacy and Information Science*. 2012; 18 (1):12-25.
6. Parse RR. **Research as evidence: Many meanings**. *Los Angeles: Sage Publications Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA*; 2013. p. 20-24.
7. Williams B, Perillo S, Brown T. **What are the factors of organizational culture in health care settings that act as barriers to the implementation of evidence-based practice? A scoping review**. *Nurse education today*. 2015; 35(2):e34-e41.
8. Labrague LJ, McEnroe-Pettite D, Taras K, D'Souza MS, Fronda DC, Mirafuentes EC, et al., editors. **Predictors of evidence-based practice knowledge, skills, and attitudes among nursing students**. *Nursing forum*; 2019: *Wiley Online Library*.
9. Naidoo JR, Adamu A. **Exploring the perceptions of registered nurses towards evidence-based practice in a selected general hospital in Nigeria**. *Africa Journal of Nursing and Midwifery*. 2015; 17(1):33-46.
10. Hadgu G, Almaz S, Tsehay SJAJNS. **Assessment of nurses' perceptions and barriers to evidence-based practice in Tikur Anbessa specialized hospital Addis Ababa Ethiopia**. *ResearchGate*. 2015; 4(3):73-83.
11. Mutisya AK, KagureKarani A, Kigonde C. **Research utilization among nurses at a teaching hospital in Kenya**. *Journal of caring sciences*. 2015; 4(2):95.

12. Davis DA, Taylor-Vaisey A. **Translating guidelines into practice: a systematic review of theoretic concepts, practical experience, and research evidence in the adoption of clinical practice guidelines.** *Cmaj.* 1997; 157(4):408-416.
13. Ross JJJoPN. **Information literacy for evidence-based practice in peri-anesthesia nurses: readiness for evidence-based practice in the USA.** *Journal of peri-anesthesia Nursing* 2010; 25(2):64-70.
14. Polit DF, Beck CT. **Nursing research: Generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice:** *Lippincott Williams & Wilkins;* 2008.
15. Morales-Asencio J, Sesé AA, Bennasar MV, Artigues GV, Perelló CC. **Nursing practice settings and competence to incorporate evidence into decisions: analysis of the situation in the Balearic Islands (Spain).** *Gaceta sanitaria.* 2011; 25(3):191-197.
16. Dereje B, Hailu E, Beharu MJAPDS. **Evidence-based Practice Utilization and Associated Factors among Nurses Working in Public Hospitals of Jimma Zone Southwest Ethiopia: A Cross-Sectional Study.** *General Medicine.* 2019; 7:321.
17. Saunders H, Vehvilainen-Julkunen K. **Nurses' Evidence-Based Practice Beliefs and the Role of Evidence-Based Practice Mentors at University Hospitals in Finland.** *Worldviews on evidence-based nursing.* 2017; 14(1):35-45.
18. Beshir MA, Woreta SA, Kebede M. **Evidence-based practice among health professionals in hospitals of Northwest Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study.** *International journal of evidence-based healthcare.* 2017; 15(4):161-170.
19. Majid S, Foo S, Luyt B, Zhang X, Zheng Y-L, Chang Y-K, et al. **Adopting evidence-based practice in clinical decision making: nurses' perceptions, knowledge, and barriers.** *Singapore Journal of the Medical Library Association.* 2011; 99(3):229.
20. Shifa F, Evans D, Bradley HJAiN. **Nurses' perceptions of barriers and facilitators to implementing EBP in the Maldives.** *Hindawi Publishing Corporation.* 2014; 2014:14.
21. SHAPIRO SS, Wilk MB. **An analysis of variance test for normality (complete samples)†in Great Britain.** *Biometrika.* 1965; 52(3-4):591-611.

22. Naidoo JR, Adamu AJAJoN, Midwifery. **Exploring the perceptions of registered nurses towards evidence-based practice in a selected general hospital in Nigeria.** 2015; 17(1):33-46.
23. Solomons NM, Spross JAJJonm. **Evidence-based practice barriers and facilitators from a continuous quality improvement perspective: an integrative review.** 2011; 19(1):109-120.
24. Strout TD, Lancaster K, Schultz AA. **Development and implementation of an inductive model for evidence-based practice: A grassroots approach for building evidence-based practice capacity in staff nurses.** *Nursing Clinics.* 2009; 44(1):93-102.
25. Jones J, Schilling K, Pesut D. **Barriers and benefits associated with nurses information seeking related to patient education needs on clinical nursing units.** *The open nursing journal.* 2011; 5:24.
26. Jordan P, Bowers C, Morton DJSAJoCC. **Barriers to implementing evidence-based practice in a private intensive care unit in the Eastern Cape.** 2016; 32(2):50-54.

Tables:

Table lists presented in the study of EBP and its associated factors among nurses working at teaching specialized hospitals in Northwest Ethiopia, 2020

Table 1: A calculated sample size of EBP by Epi Info of each factor variable from the previous cross-sectional study

Variables	category	EBP use no.	EBP not use	Prop	COR	sample size
Sex	Male	86	53	61.9	2.488	172
	Female	45	69	39.5		
Educational Level	BSc	107	61	63.7	4.458	72
	Diploma	24	61	28.2		
Current Role	Head Nurse	15	4	78.9	3.815	96
	Staff Nurse	116	118	49.6		
Knowledge	Knowledgeable	95	61	60.9	2.639	154
	Not Knowledgeable	36	61	37.1		
Lack of Autonomy to change practice	Neutral	21	24	46.7	1.718	482
	Agree	27	53	33.8		
Inability to properly interpret the result of research	Neutral	27	19	58.7	4.895	66
	Agree	18	62	22.5		

Table 2: Socio-demographic characteristics of Nurses in the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals, Ethiopia 2020 (n=507)

Variables	Categories	Male (%)	Female (%)	
Age_catagories	20-24	2.6	3.6	
	25-29	20.5	27.4	
	30-34	15	18.7	
	≥35	4.9	7.3	
Educational Level	BSc Degree	37.9	50.3	
	MSc Degree	5.1	6.7	
Work Experience	5<	21.7	27	
	5-10	18.3	23.9	
	>10	3	6.1	
Current place of work	The University of Gondar teaching Specialized Referral hospital	28	39.1	
	Tibebe Gion teaching Specialized Referral hospital	15	17.9	
Working Unit	Inpatient wards	25.2	28.8	
	ICU wards	3.7	6.5	
	Operation theater	3.2	6.1	
	Emergency wards	6.5	5.5	
	Outpatient department	4.3	10.1	
Work position	Staff nurse	38.3	53.1	
	Team leader Nurse	3.9	2.8	
	Admin nurse	0.8	1.2	
Training related to EBP	No	31.4	43.4	
	Yes	11.6	13.6	
Electronic device used	Low-end phones or	8.3	7.3	

	basic phones			
	Feature phones or internet-enabled phones	10.3	16.4	
	Smartphone	14	24.1	
	Tablet computer	1	0.4	
	Laptop Computer	5.1	6.1	
Internet access at home	No	45.7	45.7	
	Yes	4.3	4.3	

Table 3: Bi-variate and multivariable analysis of evidence-based practice among nurses of the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals, Ethiopia 2020 (n=507).

Variables	EBP		COR (95% CI)	AOR (95%CI)	P-value
	Poor	Good			
Gender					
Male	114	104	1	1	
Female	164	125	0.695(0.488-0.990)	1.39(0.95-3.03)	0.091
Educational level					
BSc	250	197	1	1	
MSc and above	18	42	2.961(1.653-5.304)	2.15(1.15-4.02)*	0.017
Availability of preferred information sources					
Available	240	226	2.03(1.03-4.01)	0.86(0.40-1.86) 0.71	
Not available	28	13	1	1	
Computer access at the workplace					
No	141	127	1	1	
Yes	94	145	1.713(1.203-2.438)	1.032(0.679-1.569) 0.888	
Internet access at the workplace					
No	144	93	1	1	
Yes	123	146	1.838(1.29-2.619)	0.968(0.598-1.566)	0.894
Administrative support					
Not supportive	218	159	1	1	
supportive	50	80	2.194(1.458-3.30)	1.89(1.22-2.91)*	0.004
Self-reported availability of enough time					
No	158	126	1	1	

Yes	110	113	1.288(0.906-1.831)	0.947(0.630-1.422)	0.791
Autonomy-to-change practice by EBP					
No	159	116	1	1	
Yes	109	123	0.87(0.75 – 1.01)	1.19(0.81 - 1.76)	0.376
Knowledge about EBP					
Poor	180	88	1	1	
Good	146	93	1.303(0.905-1.875)	0.956(0.636-1.44)	0.830
Attitude towards evidence-based practice					
Unfavorable	174	109	1	1	
Favorable	94	130	2.208(1,544-3.156)	1.80(1.24-2.62)*	0.002
Information searching Skills for evidence-based practice					
Poor	158	94	1	1	
Good	110	145	2.216(1.552-3.162)	1.385(0.904-2.121)	0.134
Preference/use of available Health Information Sources					
Not preferred	156	92	1	1	
Preferred	112	147	2.226(1.559-3.178)	2.32(1.58-3.39)**	0.000
Awareness about electronic Health Information Sources					
Not aware	148	106	1	1	
Aware	120	133	1.547(1.090-2.198)	1.142(0.76-1.71)	0.520

EBP: Evidence based practice, COR: Crude odds ratio, CI: Confidence interval, AOR: adjusted odds ratio, 1: Reference category, *: 0.001<p< 0.05, **: p<0.001

Figures:

Figure lists presented in the study of EBP and its associated factors among nurses working at teaching specialized hospitals in Northwest Ethiopia, 2020.

Fig. 1: Sampling procedure of the study of Evidence-Based Practice among nurses at the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals, 2020

Fig. 2: Evidence-Based Practice among nurses at the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals by nurses in 2020.

Fig. 3: Preferences on Sources of Evidence-Based Practice among Nurses in University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals, 2020 (n=507)

Fig. 4: Awareness about Electronic Information Sources of Evidence-Based Practice among Nurses in University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals, 2020 (n=507)

Fig. 5: Information searching skill for Evidence-Based Practice in University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals, 2020 (n=507)

Fig. 6: Nurses Self-Efficacy in Evidence-Based Practice at the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals, 2020 (n=507)

Fig. 7: *Self-reported attitudes towards evidence-based practice among Nurses in the University of Gondar and Tibebe Gion Teaching Specialized Hospitals, Ethiopia 2020.*

Keys: A= Research and literature findings are useful in day-to-day practice B= application of EBP is necessary, C= I need to increase the use of evidence, D= I am interested in learning and improving EBP skills, E= EBP improves the quality of patient care, F= my reimbursement rate will increase if I use EBP, G= EBP helps in decision making, H= my workload is not too high to keep up-to-date, I= Critical appraisal is a necessary step and J= I have access to the best resources needed for EBP

Additional file

Research Questionnaire

Instruction letter

Dear participants, Thank you for your willingness to participate in this study which aims to assess Evidence-Based Practice and its associated factors among Nurses. This questionnaire has nine sections; Scio-demographic data, Nurses Evidence-Based Practice, Knowledge on Evidence-Based Practice, Nurses Preferred Sources of Health Information, Awareness about Electronic Information Sources, information searching skills, attitude towards Evidence-Based Practice, self-efficacy for Evidence-Based Practice, and factors affecting Evidence-Based Practice. You are required to have read each question carefully and give the answer you think is correct for yourself by making a circle, fill or tick (✓) accordingly.

If you have any inquiry regarding the study, please contact on the following address.

PI Phone No: +251916248311/+251918813287

Email: abebirhanu21@gmail.com

Thank you.

Section I: Scio-demographic Data

S.N	Questions	Choices	skip
101	Age in years	_____ years	
102	Gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Male• Female	
103	Educational status	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. BSc Degree2. MSc Degree3. Ph.D. Degree	
104	Work experience in years	_____ years	
105	Current place of work	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The University of Gondar teaching Specialized Referral hospital• Tibebe Gion teaching Specialized Referral hospital	
106	Current working unit	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Inpatient departments	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICU wards • OR • Emergency wards • Outpatient Departments 	
107	Worker position	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Staff nurse 2. Team leader Nurse 3. Admin nurse 	
108	Have you ever received any training related to Evidence-Based Practice?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 	
109	When do you get the training?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undergraduate • Postgraduate 	If your answer for Q108 is "No" go to Q110
110	Which type of electronic device do you use in searching for evidence?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Low-end phones or basic phones (<i>Have only core functionalities (voice calling and SMS messaging)</i>) 2) Feature phones or internet-enabled phones (<i>can access the internet for sending an email, browsing the web, and so on (but usually without the same ease-of-use as smartphones due to smaller screens, etc.)</i>) 3) Smartphone (<i>provide voice, SMS, and internet access which can run built-in applications for a wide variety of purposes (e.g., Web browsing, calendars, document reading, and others).</i>) 4) Tablet computer 5) Laptop Computer 6) Desktop computer 	
111	Do you have internet access in your home?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Yes 2) No 	If your answer of Q110 is not 5 or 6 jump Q111 and go to the next

Section II: Nurses Evidence-Based Practice

S.N	Question	Choices			
		Never	Monthly	Weekly	Daily
201	I formulate an answerable PICO question (P: patient, interest group, nursing problem, I: new intervention or nursing method for patient, C: existing nursing intervention or comparison to compare, O: expected outcome of interest) (Ask)	1	2	3	4
202	I conduct online searches or tracked down the relevant evidence once I have formulated the PICO questions using databases and/or search engines (CINAHL, Medline, PubMed, etc.) (Acquire)	1	2	3	4
203	I can rapidly appraise studies to determine their applicability (usefulness in my clinical practice) and the validity (closeness to the truth) of the research evidence to my clinical practice (Appraise)	1	2	3	4
204	I Relate research findings to my clinical practice and point out similarities and differences (Aggregate)	1	2	3	4
205	I integrate the most up-to-date results from scientific research with my clinical experiences to solve problems related to my professional practice (Apply)	1	2	3	4
206	I collect patient outcome data to evaluate how well I achieved my nursing care plan and my evidence-based practices (Assess)	1	2	3	4
207	Once I have implemented a change and evaluated its effectiveness I share my findings and or outcomes with others in my facility. (Announce/appearance)	1	2	3	4

Section III: Nurses knowledge about Evidence-Based Practice

S.N	Questions	Yes	No	I don't know
301	Evidence-Based Practice is the integration of best research evidence, clinical expertise, and patients' values and preferences in making decisions about the care of individual patients.	1	0	9
302	Using Evidence-Based Practice increases the certainty that the selected treatment or nursing procedure will be effective	1	0	9
303	Do you know Evidence-based practice is a process of making decisions using information derived from current scientifically proven evidence?	1	0	9
304	Do you know Evidence-based practice involves a series of steps from identifying the clinical question, finding the answer/evidence, assessing the validity of evidence, to applying it if clinically suitable?	1	0	9
305	Evidence-based practice requires the use of critical appraisal skills to ensure the quality of all the research papers retrieved	1	0	9
306	A literature search using Boolean operator ("OR", "AND", "NOT" or "NEAR") would reduce the number of citations that the search would produce	1	0	9
307	The best and quickest way to find evidence is by reading textbooks.	1	0	9
308	Previous clinical experience is more important than research findings in choosing the best treatment available for a patient	1	0	9
309	Understanding of patient's preferences is essential for identifying the best available treatment for that particular patient	1	0	9
310	Do you understand and demonstrate the commonly used statistical terms (odds ratio, confidence interval, chance, bias, confounding variables, etc.) covered in the paper?	1	0	9

Section IV: Nurses Preferred Sources of Health Information

	Questions	Never	Rarely (once in a few months)	Sometimes (at least once a month)	Often (once a week)	Always (several times a Day)
401	Reading printed research articles, magazines, pamphlets	1	2	3	4	5
402	Referring to clinical practice from medical journals (HINARI...)	1	2	3	4	5
403	Reading articles from searching of electronic databases with Internet (e.g. CINAHL, Medline)	1	2	3	4	5
404	Referring medical apps (e.g. Up-to-Date, Medscape)	1	2	3	4	5
405	Referring policy and guideline manuals	1	2	3	4	5
406	Information learning from training	1	2	3	4	5
407	Information sharing from colleagues	1	2	3	4	5

Section V: Awareness about Electronic Information Sources used for getting Best evidence for Evidence-Based Practice

No	Questions	Unaware	Aware but not used in clinical decision making	Aware and used in clinical decision making
	International Journal of Medical and Health Science			
501	Centre of Evidence-based medicine (CEBM)	1	2	3
502	Google Scholar	1	2	3
503	PubMed journal	1	2	3
504	HINARI: Access to Research in Health program	1	2	3
	Databases	1	2	3
505	British Nursing index	1	2	3
506	Cochrane library(systematic reviews)	1	2	3
507	Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL)	1	2	3
508	Medline (Extensive Medical and Nursing database)	1	2	3
	Applications			
509	Medscape	1	2	3
510	Up-to-date	1	2	3
511	Medical Skills and Procedures	1	2	3

Section VI: Nurses Information searching skill for evidence-based practice

S.N	Items	Scales				
		Very poor	Poor	Neutral	Good	Very good
601	The skill of using a computer and the internet to search for online information via database and/or search engines	1	2	3	4	5
602	Skill at browsing the internet, information searching, and retrieving skills in the context of EBP	1	2	3	4	5
603	Skill at using search strategy(Index browsing (e.g. author, title, resource) Truncations/wildcards (e.g. ‘*’, ‘?’), Medical Subject Headings (MeSH), Search limits (e.g. publication date), Proximity operators (e.g. W/nn)	1	2	3	4	5
604	Skill of download and/or upload information through internet	1	2	3	4	5
605	When searching for the best clinical evidence from electronic databases, your use of Boolean operators/connectors (“OR”, “AND”, “NOT”, or “NEAR”).	1	2	3	4	5
606	Your foreign language skill to read and understand international best evidence	1	2	3	4	5

Section VII: Nurses attitude towards evidence-based practice

S.N	Items	Choices				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
701	Literature and research findings are useful in my day-to-day practice	1	2	3	4	5
702	Application of Evidence-Based Practice is necessary for the practice related to my profession	1	2	3	4	5
703	I need to increase the use of evidence in my daily practice.	1	2	3	4	5
704	I am interested in learning or improving the skills necessary to incorporate Evidence-Based Practice into my practice.	1	2	3	4	5
705	Evidence-Based Practice improves the quality of patient care.	1	2	3	4	5
706	My reimbursement rate will increase if I incorporate Evidence-Based Practice into my practice.	1	2	3	4	5
707	Evidence-Based Practice helps me to make decisions about patient care.	1	2	3	4	5

708	I believe my workload is not too high to keep up-to-date with all new evidence.	1	2	3	4	5
709	I believe that critically assessing evidence is an important step in evidence-based practice	1	2	3	4	5
710	I believe that I have access to the best resources needed to carry out evidence-based practices.	1	2	3	4	5

Section VIII: Self-Efficacy towards evidence-based practice

Instruction: the following items describe activities that support and ensure evidence-based nursing practice. Rate how confident you are that you can do each activity listed using a scale labeled by a number from 0 to 100%

S.N	Items	0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100 Not confident Moderately confident Confident		
		Not Confident	Moderately Confident	Confident
801	Routinely ask answerable questions in my clinical practice	1	2	3
802	Locate resources in my department and institution to facilitate my understanding of research literature relevant to my nursing practice	1	2	3
803	Locate and review published research studies that have relevance to nursing interventions important to my practice	1	2	3
804	Routinely identify patient outcomes to target nursing interventions	1	2	3
805	Integrate the various sources of evidence and apply them to my specialty and practice	1	2	3
806	Modify nursing interventions recommended for my patient based on characteristics of the specific unit in which I work	1	2	3
807	Routinely evaluate the research literature and other sources of evidence related to nursing interventions for my specialty population and practice	1	2	3

Section IX: Factors affecting evidence-based practice

S.N	Questions	Choices	Skip
901	Which of the following health information sources are available in your organization? (More than one choice is possible)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • paper journals • Books • Relevant practice guidelines • Access to an online database • Training manuals • All of the above • None of the above • Others, specify____ 	
902	Is there access to computers loaded with different reference materials (like books, journals, guidelines)?	1) Yes 2) No	
903	Is there internet access in your workplace?	1) Yes 2) No	If Q903 is No go to Q905
904	Is there a high speed of the internet in your working area?	1) Yes 2) No	
905	Does your facility administration support the use of current research in your clinical practice?	1) Yes 2) No	
906	Have you received formal training in search strategies for finding research relevant to your practice?	1) Yes 2) No	
907	Do you have enough time to apply evidence-based practice?	1) Yes 2) No	
908	Do you have an awareness of the research and Evidence-Based Practice?	1) Yes 2) No	
909	Do you be able to read and understand materials in English or other languages	1) Yes 2) No	

910	Do you feel that you have enough authority to change patient care procedures?	1) Yes 2) No
911	Are physicians cooperating with the EBP implementation?	1) Yes 2) No
912	Does the used statistical analysis are easily understandable?	1) Yes 2) No
913	Do literature reports have conflicting results with your clinical practice?	1) Yes 2) No
914	Are there sufficient resources (e.g. equipment, protocols, guidelines) in your facility to change practice	1) Yes 2) No
915	Rank your 3 greatest factors to the use of Evidence-Based Practice in your clinical practice.	<input type="checkbox"/> Insufficient time <input type="checkbox"/> Lack of information resources <input type="checkbox"/> Lack of research skills <input type="checkbox"/> Poor ability to critically appraise the literature <input type="checkbox"/> Inability to apply research findings to individual patients with unique characteristics <input type="checkbox"/> Lack of understanding of statistical analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Lack of collective support among my colleagues in my facility
916	In your opinion, what factors are important to be corrected for you to adopt Evidence-Based Practice?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give adequate training in searching strategies & EBP • Give protected time to conduct EBP • Access to a system for comprehensive literature searching • Mentoring by nurses who have adequate EBP experience • If others, specify_____

Thank you for your valuable response and patience!!!

የጥናቱ የአማርኛ መጠይቅ (Guiding questions for In-depth Interview Amharic Version)

1. ራስዎን አስተዋውቀውኝ እድሜዎን ከዛም መረጃን ተመርኩዞ መስራት ማለት ለእርስዎ ምን ማለት እንደሆነ ቢነግሩን? በመረጃ ላይ የተመሠረተ የነርሲንግ አገልግሎት አሰራር መርሆዎችን ለመተግበር ዕውቀቱ አለዎት? መረጃን ተመርኩዞ የመስራት ትግበራ አለ? መልስዎ አዎ ከሆነ ፣ የትኞቹ ናቸው? አዎንታዊ ውጤት አላቸው? ከሆነስ ውጤቶች ምንድን ናቸው? ቢያብራሩልኝ?
2. ስለ በመረጃ ላይ የተመሠረተ የነርሲንግ አገልግሎት አሰራር አፈፃፀም ሊነግሩኝ ይችላሉ? አስፈላጊ ነው ወይስ አይደለም? ካልሆነ ለምን? አዎ ከሆነ ብትነግረኝ(ሪኝ)? በመረጃ ላይ የተመሠረተ አሰራር አፈፃፀም ላይ ችግሮች የትኞቹ ናቸው? ያስቸግራሉ ወይስ ቀላል ናቸው? አዎ ከሆነ ፣ እንዴት?
3. በመረጃ ላይ የተመሠረተ አሰራር አፈፃፀምን እንዴት ማሻሻል እንችላለን? በመረጃ ላይ የተመሠረተ አሰራር አፈፃፀምን ለማሻሻል ዝግጁ ነዎት? አዎ ከሆነ ፣ እንዴት? ካልሆነ ለምን? ሆስፒታሉ ወይም አመራሮች በመረጃ ላይ የተመሠረተ አሰራርን ለመተግበር እገዛ ያደርጋሉ? አዎ ከሆነ እንዴት? ካልሆነ ለምን? በመረጃ ላይ የተመሠረተ አሰራርን ተግባራዊ ለማድረግ ድርጅትዎን ወይም መሪዎን እየረዱ ነው?
4. በነርሲንግ አገልግሎት የአሰራር ችግርዎ ላይ ተመስርተው የነርሶች ምርምሮችን አንብበዋል? አዎ ከሆነ ለሌሎች ለማጋራትስ ይሞክራሉ? ካልሆነ ለምን?

ጊዜዎትን ሰውተው ስለተባበሩኝ እጅግ አመሰግናለሁ።

Guiding questions for In-depth Interview (English Version)

1. Explain yourself and then what is Evidence-Based Practice (EBP) to you? Do you know to implement Evidence-Based Practice (EBP) principles? Is there any implemented Evidence-Based Practice? If yes, what are those? Are those have a positive outcome? If so what are those outcomes?
2. Can you tell me about the implementation of Evidence-Based Practice in your setting? Does it have importance or not? If not, why? If yes, tell me them? What are the problems with the implementation of Evidence-Based Practice? Is that difficult or easy? If yes, how?
3. How can we improve the implementation of Evidence-Based Practice? Are you ready to improve the implementation of Evidence-Based Practice? If yes, How? If not why? Is your organization or leaders help in implementing Evidence-Based Practice? If yes how? If not, why? Are you helping your organization or leader to implement Evidence-Based Practice?
4. Have you read nursing research based on your clinical problem? If yes are you trying to share with others? If not why? If yes how do you share?

Thank you for your valuable response and patience!!!